

CONSTITUTIONAL BASIS OF PROPERTY RIGHTS PROTECTION

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The Constitution is followed in the adoption and implementation of adopted regulatory legal instruments and property rights changes. The protection of property rights and owner rights is the goal of several provisions in our Constitution, which is regarded as the supreme law of the land. In particular, Article 41 of the Constitution guarantees everyone the right to possess property. This constitutional norm states that a citizen's age, legal competence, or rights are irrelevant when determining ownership. Stated differently, a citizen is deemed to possess property by birth, and the law offers ample avenues for this to occur.

The establishment of a layer of owners, the expropriation of state-owned property, and the acceleration of the privatization process received a lot of attention as a result of the changes carried out in Uzbekistan and the adoption of several legal instruments. The manifestation of private property's benefits, the growth of the private owner class, and the practice of supply and demand competition—which is regarded as the fundamental law of market relations—at the foundation of private property have all contributed to a significant shift in the status of private property under market conditions.

Each person develops a sense of ownership through the state's protection of their rights, the guarantee of their right to possess property, and the enrichment of their conceptions of ownership. One could argue that the Republic of Uzbekistan's Constitution has strengthened property rights even more with the revision to Article 68, Part 2.

Both individuals and legal companies may privatize land in our nation. Plots: Individuals or groups may privatize land plots in accordance with the Law "On Privatization of Land Plots Not Intended for Agriculture."

A citizen who owns private property on land is entitled to the following: 1) land sales by private land owners; 2) land donations; 3) land exchanges; 4) pledges; and 5) inheritances.

Most significantly, only with the owner's permission and in a contract at market value may the state repurchase such land for public purposes. In other words, land does not belong in "snos" and can only be alienated if the state purchases it for a predetermined sum.

In addition, the constitutional requirements outlined in the article guarantee the proper use of privatized land and its preservation for future generations, acknowledging that land is a valuable national asset and a significant economic resource that must not be treated as landless.

Each person's ownership of property indicates that they all have an equal right to do so. According to Article 19 of our Constitution, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social background, faith, or personal or social standing, all citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan enjoy the same rights and freedoms and are treated equally before the law. No matter how much or how little property there is, our current legal system guarantees that everyone has equal rights and that no owner's rights are more valuable than those of other owners.

Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On Expropriation and Privatization," states that the following parties may be the subjects of public property purchases as well as the privatization of state property objects: citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, other nations, stateless individuals, non-state legal entities, and foreign legal entities. captured. Each person has many options to become an owner under our legislation, which also ensures that their rights will be protected.

Ensuring the inviolability of all types of property under market conditions is seen as crucial for the successful implementation of economic changes. "Economic Foundations of Society" is the title of Chapter XII of the Constitution. Article 65, first part, states that "the basis of the economy of Uzbekistan, aimed at increasing the welfare of citizens, is the property of various forms." The state prioritizes the rights of consumers while establishing the framework for the growth of market relations and fair competition. It also ensures the freedom of labor, entrepreneurship, and economic activity.

This constitutional provision does not restrict the amount of property; rather, it expresses the possibility of various forms of property. Two types of property are defined by Article 167 of the Republic of Uzbekistan's Civil Code:

There are two types of property:

- 1) private;
- 2) public.

The state assures the protection of property and upholds the equality of rights required for the emergence of various forms of property. Property's legal status and regime are intrinsically tied to the separation of property into several types.

The topics of "demolition of housing" and "snos" were settled at the level of legal documents prior to the new constitution's approval. The idea that this matter would be decided at the level of the Constitution seemed like a pipe dream to many owners. Given the gravity of the situation, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan stressed during his inauguration in 2021 that private property privacy must be regulated first. The recently amended constitution states that the nation owes itself a great deal. He is making an effort to complete the important duty of sheltering the populace.

The head of state personally introduced these articles, which were then debated at the commission on constitutional change meeting as a proposal pertaining to the question of housing inviolability and damages to housing recompense.

This standard demonstrates unequivocally that Uzbekistan is becoming the social state envisioned in the Constitution's first article. In the event that they broke the law, citizens might now employ legal protection or obtain compensation thanks to this new rule.

REFERENCE:

1. Hakimov, S. (2023). SPORT KONTRAKTLARIDA MAJBURIYATLAR BAJARILISHINI TA'MINLASHNING AHAMIYATI. Talqin va tadqiqotlar, 1(14);
2. Hakimov, S. (2023). SPORT KONTRAKTLARIDA NEUSTOYKANING QO 'LLANILISHI. Talqin va tadqiqotlar, 1(26);
3. Muhammadjon Otabek Ogli Tursunov (2023). O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIMNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH: YUTUQLAR VA MUAMMOLAR. Scientific progress, 4 (2), 213-217;
4. Tursunov, Mukhammadjon Otabek Ugli (2022). APPLICATION OF ECONOMIC RESTRICTIONS (SANCTIONS) IN INTERNATIONAL LAW: PRACTICAL AND THEORETICAL ASPECTS. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2 (5), 903-912;
5. Ilkhombekov, J. (2022). THE ROLE AND ROLE OF THE MEDIA IN THE INFORMATION DISTRIBUTION PROCESS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 1(17), 80-84;
6. Ilhombekov Jasurbek. Comparative Legal Analysis of Reforms Conducted for the Development of the Information Sector in the New

Uzbekistan. AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies. Volume 02, Issue 01, 2024 ISSN (E):2993-2157;

7. o‘g‘li, H. S. F. (2024). Concept, Essence, Legal Aspect and Guarantees of Public Associations. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 2(2), 365–369. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPDIS/article/view/3309>